

Pappalysin 1 or pregnancy-associated plasma protein A or insulin-like growth factor-dependent IGF binding protein-4 protease (PAPPA) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : PAPPA encodes a secreted metalloproteinase which cleaves insulin-like growth factor binding proteins (IGFBPs). A metalloproteinase, or metalloprotease, is an enzyme whose catalytic mechanism involves a metal. Pappalysin-1 is used in screening tests for Down syndrome. It has been implicated in endometrial cancer, denervation-induced muscle atrophy, pre-eclampsia, ovarian carcinomas, cellular senescence, atherosclerosis, neointimal hyperplasia, acute coronary syndrome, corticogenesis, gestational diabetes mellitus and colon cancer, to name a few. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of PAPPA, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible

*ML dicoveries of PAPPA synergy in Meningiomas

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hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: PAPPa, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplas-

tic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagioccephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. Pappalysin 1 (PAPPA)

Lin et al. [13] studied 4 pregnancy-associated plasma proteins (PAPP's) using 206 plasma samples from 175 pregnant women between 12 and 44 week of gestation. The measured concentration of three PAPP's (A/C/D) showed a gradual but small rate of increase during the 2nd trimester, which became more rapid in the 3rd trimester. Fur-

ther, they observed that PAPP-A continued to rise steadily during this period, while PAPP-C/D tended to reach a plateau.

Bischof [14] isolated PAPP-A from late pregnancy plasma. They found it to be an α 2-glycoprotein of 750-820 000 MW, probably a dimer with each monomer being composed of 2 polypeptide chains of 218000 MW. Further, the amino acid composition and other physicochemical characteristics are found to be similar to human α 2-macroglobulin. In vitro, they found that PAPP-A exhibited an inhibition of the activity of the complement system, of the caseinolytic activity of plasmin and possibly of the urokinase activation of plasminogen. Caseinolytic activity has been found in acute human wound fluid and is thought to be involved in the breakdown of damaged proteins and the repair process (He et al. [15]). Urokinase is a thrombolytic (Thrombolysis or fibrinolytic therapy, is the breakdown (lysis) of blood clots formed in blood vessels) enzyme mainly formed in the kidney and excreted in the urine which converts plasminogen into plasmin and promotes the dissolution of physiologically-occurring blood clots; for example, as in menstrual blood (Polifka and Habermann [16]). Thus they proposed the hypothesis that PAPP-A played a role in the regulation of fibrinolysis during pregnancy.

Oxvig et al. [17] demonstrated the existence of an association between PAPP-A and the proform of eosinophil major basic protein (proMBP). This is confirmed by PAPP-A being a disulfide-bridged complex with proMBP (PAPP-A/proMBP).

PAPP-A was found to be one of the most promising four biochemical markers in maternal serum for first trimester screening for Down's syndrome (Wald et al. [18]).

Kristensen et al. [19] determined the amino acid sequence of human PAPP-A, which is a component of the circulating complex with the proform of eosinophil major basic protein (proMBP). Intact insulin-like growth factor binding protein IGFBP-4 is an inhibitor of IGF action in vitro, and cleavage of IGFBP-4 has been shown to abolish its ability to inhibit insulin-like growth factor (IGF) stimulatory effects in a variety of systems. This suggests that IGFBP-4 proteolysis acts as a positive regulator of IGF bioavailability. Lawrence et al. [20] reported the isolation of an IGF-dependent IGFBP-4-specific protease from human fibroblast-conditioned media and its identification as PAPP-A, a protein of unknown function found in high concentrations in the maternal circulation during pregnancy. Further, they purified PAPP-A from pregnancy serum and found IGF-dependent IGFBP-4 protease activity. In conclusion, they identified an IGF-dependent IGFBP protease and at the same time assigned a function to PAPP-A, which in their analysis represented an unanticipated union of two areas of research that were not linked in any way earlier.

1.3. Roles of PAPP-A in different disease

N6-methyladenosine (m^6A) mRNA methylation has been considered a gene modulatory mechanism involved in disease progression and carcinogenesis. Ruan et al. [21] explored the mechanism of m^6A mRNA methylation in **endometrial cancer**. They observed reduced levels of m^6A methylation, METTL3, and IGFBP4 in tumor tissues of patients with endometrial cancer, and SRAMP analysis confirmed that IGFBP4 and PAPP-A had m^6A methylation sites. Further, they found that reduced m^6A methylation promoted endometrial cancer cell progression and tumor formation in vivo and

m⁶A methylation of RNA in endometrial cancer cells directly modulated IGFBP4 and PAPP-A expression.

Denervation-induced muscle atrophy is a frequent cause of skeletal muscle diseases. Martin et al. [22] studied the time-dependent changes in the insulin-like growth factor (IGF1):IGF-1 binding protein (IGFBP5):PAPP-A system and its regulators in gastrocnemius muscle after sciatic denervation. They observed gastrocnemius atrophy and overexpression of IGF-1 from day 3 post-denervation and expression of both IGFBP-5 and pappalysins were found to be increased on days 1 and 3. Further, the ratio IGFBP-5/PAPP-A was found to be correlated with the main proteolytic markers. Their data pointed to the fact that the initial increase of pappalysins could facilitate the IGF-1 action on muscle growth, whereas their subsequent decrease could lead to further muscle wasting.

Xv et al. [23] investigated the clinical value of using urothelial cancer-associated 1 (UCA1) and microRNA-16 (miR-16) as biomarkers for the diagnosis of **pre-eclampsia** (PE). In their study, they also compared the diagnostic values of miR-16, UCA1 and PAPP-A in PE and further investigated the interaction between miR-16 and UCA1/PAPP-A. To conduct the study, they enrolled 128 PE patients and 172 healthy pregnant women. They found that compared with miR-16 and PAPP-A, UCA1 exhibited a better value in the diagnosis of PE. Further the expression of PAPP-A and UCA1 was down-regulated while the expression of miR-16 was up-regulated in patients with PE, especially in patients with HELLP pregnancies. Also, UCA1 identified as a sponge of miR-16, while PAPP-A mRNA identified as a virtual target gene of miR-16. Finally, they observed a negative regulatory relationship between the expression of miR-16 and UCA1 or PAPP-A, while there was a positive relation between the expressions of UCA1 and PAPP-A.

PAPP-A/A2 modulate insulin-like growth factor (IGF) action and are inhibited by the stanniocalcins (STC-1/2). Hjortebjerg et al. [24] previously demonstrated increased PAPP-A and IGF activity in ascites from women with **ovarian carcinomas**. Next, in the longitudinal study of 107 women with ovarian cancer and ascites accumulation, Hjortebjerg et al. [24] determined corresponding serum and ascites levels of IGF-1/2, PAPP-A/A2 and STC-1/2 and assessed their relationship with mortality. They found that, as compared to serum, there were highly increased ascites levels of PAPP-A (51-fold) and PAPP-A2 (4-fold). Further, they also observed elevated levels for IGF-1 (12%), STC1 (90%) and STC2 (68%). In contrast, IGF-2 was reduced by 29% in ascites.

Sirtuins are pro-longevity genes with chromatin modulation potential. Bi et al. [25] generated a panel of isogenic human stem cell lines with SIRT1-SIRT7 knockouts and found that any sirtuin deficiency led to accelerated **cellular senescence**. Further, in all sirtuin-deficient human stem cell lines, they found that chromatin contacts were rewired to promote aberrant activation of PAPP-A. It is known that PAPP-A controls the pro-senescence effects associated with sirtuin deficiency.

Conover [26] reviewed the multiple role of PAPP-A with a focus on **atherosclerosis, neointimal hyperplasia, and acute coronary syndrome** in animal models and in humans.

Generating cortical neurons in accurate numbers depends on cell signaling governed by primary cilia to coordinate the proliferation and differentiation of cortical stem cells.

To investigate the multiple ciliary roles in **corticogenesis**, Basu et al. [27] explored specific mechanisms downstream of cilia signaling. They previously showed that an excess of early-born cortical neurons in mice mutant for the ciliary gene INPP5E was rescued by re-introducing GLI3 repressor. They identified novel GLI3 target genes via comparison of expression profiles between INPP5E and GLI3 mutants. Their approach highlighted the transcription factor gene SALL3 and PAPP-A, as upregulated genes in both mutants. Their further examination revealed that GLI3 directly bound to SALL3 and PAPP-A enhancers and suppressed their activity in the dorsal telencephalon.

Balkas and Celen [28] evaluated the association between **gestational diabetes mellitus** (GDM), including insulin-dependent GDM with PAPP-A multiples of the median (MoM) and free β human chorionic gonadotropin (free β -hCG) MoM levels, and assessed their potential as predictive risk factors. They observed that low serum PAPP-A MoM levels were significantly associated with the development of GDM, including insulin-dependent cases.

Cai et al. [29] investigated the role and regulatory mechanism of circular RNA PAPPa (circ-PAPPa; hsa_circ_0088233) in **colon cancer** (CC). They observed that circ-PAPPa was upregulated in CC and was negatively correlated with benign pathological features. Further, they found that silencing of circ-PAPPa inhibited the growth and glycolysis of CC cells through upregulating microRNA miR-656-3p. Further, they hypothesized that G-protein subunit Gamma-5 (GNG5), a target of miR-656-3p, could reverse the impacts of silencing circ-PAPPa on CC cells.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are

conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [30] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [31] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [31].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [32]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005.

In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [33], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [30] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [30]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [34], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores

for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. PAPP related synergies

Note - PAPP was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2^{nd} order combinations of PAPP were recorded.

3.1.1. PAPP - individual genes

The following genes in combination with PAPP showed high rankings - prominin 1 (PROM1), flavin containing dimethylaniline monooxygenase 1 (FMO1), insulin like growth factor 1 (IGF1), elastin (ELN), LIM and cysteine rich domains 1 (LMCD1), solute carrier family 12 member 1 (SLC12A1), fibulin 1 (FBLN1), integrin subunit alpha 8 (ITGA8), semaphorin 5B (SEMA5B), seizure related 6 homolog like (SEZ6L),

tripartite motif containing 9 (TRIM9), polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 16 (GALNT16), Ras association domain family member 2 (RASSF2), sushi repeat containing protein X-linked (SRPX), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 1 inhibitor (PCSK1N), solute carrier family 17 member 7 (SLC17A7), olfactomedin 2 (OLFM2), transmembrane protein 59 like (TMEM59L), secreted frizzled related protein 4 (SFRP4), AE binding protein 1 (AEBP1), cadherin related 23 (CDH23), Kazal type serine peptidase inhibitor domain 1 (KAZALD1), bone marrow stromal cell antigen 1 (BST1), neurexin 2 (NRXN2), GLI family zinc finger 1 (GLI1), cut like homeobox 2 (CUX2), ST8 alpha-N-acetyl-neuraminide alpha-2,8-sialyltransferase 1 (ST8SIA1), SPARC related modular calcium binding 2 (SMOC2), lysyl oxidase (LOX), natriuretic peptide receptor 3 (NPR3), podocalyxin like 2 (PODXL2), solute carrier family 30 member 3 (SLC30A3), lysyl oxidase like 3 (LOXL3), proteoglycan 4 (PRG4), hippocalcin like 4 (HPCAL4), connective tissue growth factor (CTGF / CCN2), tripartite motif containing 67 (TRIM67), latent transforming growth factor beta binding protein 2 (LTBP2), proteolipid protein 1 (PLP1), RUNX family transcription factor 2 (RUNX2), lysosomal associated membrane protein family member 5 (LAMP5), MBL associated serine protease 1 (MASP1), kinesin family member 1A (KIF1A), podocan like 1 (PODNL1), matrilin 3 (MATN3), serpin family F member 1 (SERPINF1), solute carrier family 14 member 2 (SLC14A2), peripherin (PRPH), Fas apoptotic inhibitory molecule 2 (FAIM2), sodium voltage-gated channel alpha subunit 7 (SCN7A), tetratricopeptide repeat domain 29 (TTC29), thrombospondin 1 (THBS1), integrin subunit alpha 11 (ITGA11), dual oxidase 1 (DUOX1), semaphorin 6D (SEMA6D), luteinizing hormone/choriogonadotropin receptor (LHCGR), retinol binding protein 4 (RBP4), dual oxidase maturation factor 1 (DUOXA1), dual oxidase 2 (DUOX2), fibroblast growth factor 7 (FGF7), NKD inhibitor of Wnt signaling pathway 1 (NKD1), reticulocalbin 3 (RCN3), forkhead associated phosphopeptide binding domain 1 (FHAD1), neurexophilin 2 (NXPH2), BOC cell adhesion associated, oncogene regulated (BOC), dishevelled associated activator of morphogenesis 2 (DAAM2), cholinergic receptor nicotinic beta 3 subunit (CHRN3), neurotrophic receptor tyrosine kinase 2 (NTRK2), dopamine receptor D2 (DRD2), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A member 6 (KCNA6), thyroid hormone receptor beta (THRB), ADAM metalloproteinase with thrombospondin type 1 motif 12 (ADAMTS12), phosphotyrosine interaction domain containing 1 (PID1), ABI family member 3 binding protein (ABI3BP), phosphodiesterase 1C (PDE1C), matrix metalloproteinase 16 (MMP16), protein phosphatase 2 regulatory subunit Bbeta (PPP2R2B), exostosin like glycosyltransferase 1 (EXTL1), S100 calcium binding protein B (S100B), collagen type XXVI alpha 1 chain (COL26A1), C1q and TNF related 7 (C1QTNF7), coagulation factor II thrombin receptor like 2 (F2RL2), Rho related BTB domain containing 3 (RHOBTB3), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 2 (DACT2), somatomedin B and thrombospondin type 1 domain containing (SBSPON), carbonic anhydrase 3 (CA3), sushi, von Willebrand factor type A, EGF and pentraxin domain containing 1 (SVEP1), heat shock protein family A (Hsp70) member 12A (HSPA12A), PDZ domain containing ring finger 4 (PDZRN4), transmembrane protein 130 (TMEM130), nicotinamide N-methyltransferase (NNMT), armadillo repeat containing 4 (ARMC4), carnitine palmitoyltransferase 1C (CPT1C), serine/threonine kinase 32A (STK32A), secretogranin II (SCG2), sushi domain containing 5 (SUSD5), CD248 molecule (CD248), dynein axonemal heavy chain 12 (DNAH12),

purinergic receptor P2Y14 (P2RY14), serine rich and transmembrane domain containing 1 (SERTM1), phospholipase C beta 1 (PLCB1), neurotrimin (NTM), regulator of G protein signaling 6 (RGS6), pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase 1 (PYCR1), nebulin (NEB), family with sequence similarity 43 member B (FAM43B), transmembrane protein 119 (TMEM119), olfactomedin like 1 (OLFML1), dual specificity phosphatase 5 pseudogene 1 (DUSP5P1), adrenoceptor alpha 2C (ADRA2C), protein kinase D1 (PRKD1), colony stimulating factor 1 (CSF1), fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2 (FLRT2), protein kinase cGMP-dependent 1 (PRKG1), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily Z member 1 (CYP4Z1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily X member 1 (CYP4X1), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A5, pseudogene (ANKRD20A5P), reticulon 4 receptor like 2 (RTN4RL2), A-kinase anchoring protein 19 (C2orf88 / AKAP19), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 8 (ENTPD8), placenta associated 9 (PLAC9), nuclear GTPase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), family with sequence similarity 180 member A (FAM180A), serine/threonine kinase 31 (STK31), family with sequence similarity 180 member B (FAM180B), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 3 (DACT3), adenosine deaminase RNA specific B1 (ADARB1), sialophorin (SPN), chromosome 2 open reading frame 27A (C2orf27A / LINC03124), C-type lectin domain containing 9A (CLEC9A), DLG associated protein 2 (DLGAP2), metallothionein 1F (MT1F), integrin subunit beta like 1 (ITGBL1), matrix metalloproteinase 17 (MMP17), delta like canonical Notch ligand 1 (DLL1), zinc finger protein 521 (ZNF521), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYS3), dual specificity phosphatase and pro isomerase domain containing 1 (DUSP27 / DUSP29), RNA, U6 small nuclear 529, pseudogene (RNU6-529P), ras homolog family member T1 pseudogene 2 (RHOT1P2), phospholipid phosphatase 4 (PLPP4), synaptotagmin 15 (SYT15), family with sequence similarity 155 member A (FAM155A), transmembrane protein 240 (TMEM240), vitrin (VIT), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A11, pseudogene (ANKRD20A11P), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 2 (HACD2), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), high mobility group box 3 pseudogene 7 (HMGB3P7), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A11, pseudogene (ANKRD20A11P), teneurin transmembrane protein 3 (TENM3), RFPL1 antisense RNA 1 (RFPL1S), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 937 (LINC00937), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1907 (LINC01907), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1), LMCD1 antisense RNA 1 (LMCD1-AS1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily F member 29, pseudogene (CYP4F29P), zinc finger protein 883 (ZNF883) and sorting nexin 18 pseudogene 13 (SNX18P13).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of PAPPAs with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - ● Individual members w.r.t PAPPAs with PAPPAs - > PROM1 / FMO1 / IGF1 / ELN / LMCD1 / SLC12A1 / FBLN1 / ITGA8 / SEMA5B / SEZ6L / TRIM9 / GALNT16 / RASSF2 / SRPX / PCSK1N / SLC17A7 / OLFM2 / TMEM59L

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS PAPP									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T PAPP									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
PROM1 - PAPP	366	297	290	353	FMO1 - PAPP	292	223	287	338
IGF1 - PAPP	244	281	291	324	ELN - PAPP	246	109	250	328
LMCD1 - PAPP	316	288	266	390	SLC12A1 - PAPP	285	250	334	52
FBLN1 - PAPP	267	266	278	267	ITGA8 - PAPP	301	202	219	285
SEMA5B - PAPP	243	221	234	297	SEZ6L - PAPP	194	347	276	288
TRIM9 - PAPP	283	240	298	301	GALNT16 - PAPP	231	235	184	261
RASSF2 - PAPP	131	278	263	356	SRPX - PAPP	332	269	260	391
PCSK1N - PAPP	191	308	248	321	SLC17A7 - PAPP	308	222	268	350
OLFM2 - PAPP	239	255	251	355	TMEM59L - PAPP	273	243	225	377
SFRP4 - PAPP	253	322	280	384	AEBP1 - PAPP	259	287	265	332
CDH23 - PAPP	226	134	237	238	KAZALD1 - PAPP	219	267	166	274
BST1 - PAPP	293	300	256	361	NRXN2 - PAPP	257	185	267	334
GLI1 - PAPP	158	265	212	309	CUX2 - PAPP	225	227	198	303
ST8SIA1 - PAPP	351	295	303	39	SMOC2 - PAPP	255	190	226	308
LOX - PAPP	204	275	133	210	NPR3 - PAPP	289	321	277	351
PODXL2 - PAPP	269	276	272	379	SLC30A3 - PAPP	335	313	337	336
LOXL3 - PAPP	154	254	245	246	PRG4 - PAPP	297	282	273	386
HPCAL4 - PAPP	227	306	253	365	CTGF - PAPP	166	279	231	279
TRIM67 - PAPP	322	339	321	382	LTBP2 - PAPP	299	234	285	366
PLP1 - PAPP	282	344	264	375	RUNX2 - PAPP	216	170	202	317
LAMP5 - PAPP	356	325	347	10	MASP1 - PAPP	241	230	286	339
KIF1A - PAPP	298	290	333	330	PODNL1 - PAPP	276	270	293	387
MATN3 - PAPP	324	268	114	371	SERPINF1 - PAPP	307	272	242	374
SLC14A2 - PAPP	291	91	211	204	PRPH - PAPP	274	197	305	313
FAIM2 - PAPP	213	237	124	206	SCN7A - PAPP	306	277	343	2
TTC29 - PAPP	270	236	283	352	THBS1 - PAPP	304	314	295	318
ITGA11 - PAPP	203	263	254	289	DUOX1 - PAPP	272	216	187	388
SEMA6D - PAPP	302	252	255	251	LHCGR - PAPP	359	334	360	307
RBP4 - PAPP	370	368	308	8	DUOXA1 - PAPP	262	95	282	333
DUOX2 - PAPP	323	326	307	362	FGF7 - PAPP	383	327	326	6
NKD1 - PAPP	340	324	361	320	RCN3 - PAPP	242	289	249	315
FHAD1 - PAPP	248	62	257	240	NXPH2 - PAPP	386	320	318	155
BOC - PAPP	233	244	196	245	DAAM2 - PAPP	277	303	288	312
CHRN3 - PAPP	352	315	284	280	NTRK2 - PAPP	205	302	297	369
DRD2 - PAPP	330	298	299	326	KCNA6 - PAPP	331	309	309	311
THRB - PAPP	114	259	233	254	ADAMTS12 - PAPP	200	316	50	319
PID1 - PAPP	319	284	236	373	ABI3BP - PAPP	303	238	207	372
PDE1C - PAPP	343	310	328	9	MMP16 - PAPP	334	205	178	298
PPP2R2B - PAPP	314	204	270	327	EXTL1 - PAPP	258	59	214	260
S100B - PAPP	321	311	313	12	COL26A1 - PAPP	341	317	350	299

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between PAPP VS Individual members.

/ SFRP4 / AEBP1 / CDH23 / KAZALD1 / BST1 / NRXN2 / GLI1 / CUX2 / ST8SIA1 / SMOC2 / LOX / NPR3 / PODXL2 / SLC30A3 / LOXL3 / PRG4 / HPCAL4 / CTGF / TRIM67 / LTBP2 / PLP1 / RUNX2 / LAMP5 / MASP1 / KIF1A / PODNL1 / MATN3 / SERPINF1 / SLC14A2 / PRPH / FAIM2 / SCN7A / TTC29 / THBS1 / ITGA11 / DUOX1 / SEMA6D / LHCGR / RBP4 / DUOXA1 / DUOX2 / FGF7 / NKD1 / RCN3 / FHAD1 / NXPH2 / BOC / DAAM2 / CHRN3 / NTRK2 / DRD2 / KCNA6 / THRB / ADAMTS12 / PID1 / ABI3BP / PDE1C / MMP16 / PPP2R2B / EXTL1 / S100B / COL26A1 / C1QTNF7 / F2RL2 / RHOBTB3 / DACT2 / SBSPON / CA3 / SVEP1 / HSPA12A / PDZRN4 / TMEM130 / NNMT / ARMC4 / CPT1C / STK32A /

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS PAPPA									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T PAPPA									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
C1QTNF7 - PAPPA	275	332	296	1	F2RL2 - PAPPA	47	286	292	281
RHOBTB3 - PAPPA	232	301	301	376	DACT2 - PAPPA	208	131	230	255
SBSPO1 - PAPPA	305	246	157	211	CA3 - PAPPA	278	323	294	385
SVEP1 - PAPPA	153	258	228	290	HSPA12A - PAPPA	206	218	216	359
PDZRN4 - PAPPA	287	312	274	367	TMEM130 - PAPPA	326	375	315	11
NNMT - PAPPA	290	285	262	380	ARMC4 - PAPPA	105	219	244	236
CPT1C - PAPPA	224	71	275	349	STK32A - PAPPA	354	247	329	360
SCG2 - PAPPA	361	318	302	13	SUSD5 - PAPPA	256	66	217	305
CD248 - PAPPA	247	16	213	227	DNAH12 - PAPPA	286	150	252	286
P2RY14 - PAPPA	279	203	192	241	SERTM1 - PAPPA	337	307	341	202
PLCB1 - PAPPA	252	232	159	304	NTM - PAPPA	263	253	259	389
RGS6 - PAPPA	296	283	338	363	PYCR1 - PAPPA	360	384	389	32
NEB - PAPPA	375	377	376	109	FAM43B - PAPPA	380	341	319	106
TMEM119 - PAPPA	348	345	325	5	OLFML1 - PAPPA	377	371	310	259
DUSP5P1 - PAPPA	385	337	367	117	ADRA2C - PAPPA	318	357	353	164
PRKD1 - PAPPA	266	329	314	325	CSF1 - PAPPA	372	374	372	49
FLRT2 - PAPPA	368	365	324	272	PRKG1 - PAPPA	392	389	349	119
SHC4 - PAPPA	374	336	351	277	CYP4Z1 - PAPPA	381	351	357	50
CYP4X1 - PAPPA	382	376	369	45	ANKRD20A5P - PAPPA	320	201	335	3
RTN4RL2 - PAPPA	379	386	384	64	C2orf88 - PAPPA	336	370	382	172
KBTBD12 - PAPPA	313	380	391	174	LDLRAD2 - PAPPA	315	328	342	357
ENTPD8 - PAPPA	339	358	323	198	PLAC9 - PAPPA	350	299	354	354
NUGGC - PAPPA	236	333	330	189	FAM180A - PAPPA	264	296	339	364
STK31 - PAPPA	325	360	388	112	FAM180B - PAPPA	160	292	289	344
DACT3 - PAPPA	373	354	370	110	ADARB1 - PAPPA	347	382	379	145
SPN - PAPPA	371	369	362	85	C2orf27A - PAPPA	390	379	355	17
CLEC9A - PAPPA	338	356	380	278	DLGAP2 - PAPPA	202	352	327	370
MT1F - PAPPA	300	385	336	92	ITGBL1 - PAPPA	364	362	365	77
MMP17 - PAPPA	317	335	320	316	DLL1 - PAPPA	327	361	371	235
ZNF521 - PAPPA	344	330	340	4	RYR3 - PAPPA	349	342	359	293
DUSP27 - PAPPA	387	391	377	23	RNU6-529P - PAPPA	389	383	390	29
SYT15 - PAPPA	281	367	392	14	FAM155A - PAPPA	333	364	317	226
ANKRD20A11P - PAPPA	223	294	304	392	HACD2 - PAPPA	392	350	386	82
GPX3 - PAPPA	353	331	311	335	HMGB3P7 - PAPPA	346	349	352	294
ANKRD20A11P - PAPPA	223	294	304	392	TENM3 - PAPPA	148	338	346	323
RFPL1S - PAPPA	378	381	375	142	LINC00937 - PAPPA	384	387	368	24
LINC01907 - PAPPA	388	392	345	130	ITGB2-AS1 - PAPPA	376	346	373	314
LMCD1-AS1 - PAPPA	284	363	366	131	CYP4F29P - PAPPA	288	248	331	343
ZNF883 - PAPPA	345	390	387	116	SNX18P13 - PAPPA	311	319	332	378

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between PAPPA VS Individual members.

SCG2 / SUSD5 / CD248 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / SERTM1 / PLCB1 / NTM / RGS6 / PYCR1 / NEB / FAM43B / TMEM119 / OLFML1 / DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C / PRKD1 / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / SHC4 / CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 / ANKRD20A5P / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / FAM180A / STK31 / FAM180B / DACT3 / ADARB1 / SPN / C2orf27A / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / MT1F / ITGBL1 / MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 / SYT15 / FAM155A / TMEM240 / VIT / ANKRD20A11P / HACD2 / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P / TENM3 / RFPL1S / LINC00937 / LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / CYP4F29P / ZNF883 / SNX18P13.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t PAPPA	
PROM1 / FMO1 / IGF1 / ELN / LMCD1 / SLC12A1 ...	
FBLN1 / ITGA8 / SEMA5B / SEZ6L / TRIM9 / GALNT16 ...	
RASSF2 / SRPX / PCSK1N / SLC17A7 / OLFM2 / TMEM59L ...	
SFRP4 / AEBP1 / CDH23 / KAZALD1 / BST1 / NRXN2 ...	
GLI1 / CUX2 / ST8SIA1 / SMOC2 / LOX / NPR3 / PODXL2 ...	
SLC30A3 / LOXL3 / PRG4 / HPCAL4 / CTGF / TRIM67 ...	
LTBP2 / PLP1 / RUNX2 / LAMP5 / MASP1 / KIF1A ...	
PODNL1 / MATN3 / SERPINF1 / SLC14A2 / PRPH / FAIM2 ...	
SCN7A / TTC29 / THBS1 / ITGA11 / DUOX1 / SEMA6D ...	
LHCGR / RBP4 / DUOXA1 / DUOX2 / FGF7 / NKD1 / RCN3 ...	
FHAD1 / NXPH2 / BOC / DAAM2 / CHRNB3 / NTRK2 / DRD2 ...	
KCNA6 / THRB / ADAMTS12 / PID1 / ABI3BP / PDE1C ...	
MMP16 / PPP2R2B / EXTL1 / S100B / COL26A1 / C1QTNF7 ...	
F2RL2 / RHOBTB3 / DACT2 / SBSPON / CA3 / SVEP1 ...	
HSPA12A / PDZRN4 / TMEM130 / NNMT / ARMC4 / CPT1C ...	
STK32A / SCG2 / SUSD5 / CD248 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 ...	
SERTM1 / PLCB1 / NTM / RGS6 / PYCR1 / NEB / FAM43B ...	
TMEM119 / OLFML1 / DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C / PRKD1 / CSF1 ...	
FLRT2 / PRKG1 / SHC4 / CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 / ANKRD20A5P ...	
RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / PLAC9 ...	
NUGGC / FAM180A / STK31 / FAM180B / DACT3 / ADARB1 ...	
SPN / C2orf27A / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / MT1F / ITGBL1 ...	
MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / DUSP27 / RNU6-529P ...	
RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 / SYT15 / FAM155A / TMEM240 / VIT ...	
ANKRD20A11P / HACD2 / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P ...	
TENM3 / RFPL1S / LINC00937 / LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 ...	
LMCD1-AS1 / CYP4F29P / ZNF883 / SNX18P13	PAPPA

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between PAPPA and Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic PAPPA 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of PAPPA-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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